

POLY (VINYL ALCOHOL) COMPOSITE WITH NANODIAMOND

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SUMMARY

Poly (vinyl alcohol)(PVA)/nanodiamond (ND) particulate composite was prepared by simply casting PVA/ND aqueous suspension. Structural studies revealed that ND particles were well dispersed in PVA. Young's modulus of the nanocomposite was 2.5 times higher than that of PVA, even with only 1 wt% loading of ND. In addition, thermal properties were improved.

Keywords: Poly(vinyl alcohol), Nanodiamond, Nanocomposite, Nano-Dispersion, Young's modulus

INTRODUCTION

Since the methodologies on well-dispersion of nano-particles were developed, polymer nanocomposites attract many attentions not only in the scientific fields, but also in the industrial applications. The emerging research area of polymer nanocomposites has received great interest due to the ability of nano-sized fillers, such as layered silicates and carbon nanotubes, to significantly improve polymer properties compared with polymer alone or micro-sized fillers composites. The potential improvements include enhanced mechanical strength, weight reduction, increased heat-resistance and improved barrier properties.

Diamond has been widely used in a variety of areas because of its excellent properties, such as the highest bulk modulus, high wear resistance, chemical inertness, good electrical insulating properties, the highest thermal conductivity and so on. It is of considerable interest to impart the excellent properties of diamond in polymer composite by incorporation of diamond particles into bulk polymeric materials [1]. In recent years, nanodiamond (ND) was exploited in some fields of nanotechnology. For example, there is a growing interest in the utilization of thin nanocrystalline diamond (NCD) films as a material for optics, electronics and biosensor applications because of diamond's superior physical properties and bio-compatibility ND has been produced by several procedures such as explosion, chemical vapor deposition, high pressure and high temperature, shock wave etc. ND is expected to offer polymer nanocomposites optimal properties because of its smooth surface, excellent optical, mechanical and thermal properties, which can approach the values of single diamond crystal [2].

Poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) is well known as a water-soluble polymer and widely used as fiber, film, adhesive, gel and stabilizer of polymer and inorganic particles [3, 4].

In addition, PVA extends the industrial applications in optical, pharmaceutical, medical, and membrane fields.

In this study, PVA/ND nanocomposite was prepared, and its structure and properties were investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sample Preparation

ND aqueous suspension (2.75 wt% of ND) was supplied from Bando Chem. Ind., Ltd. Prior to adding PVA, as-received ND aqueous suspension was dispersed by ultrasonication for 1 h. PVA was supplied from Nippon Synthetic Chemical Industry Co. Ltd, with its commercial name “Gohsenol NH-18” (DS>99 %, DP=1800). PVA powder was added to the ND aqueous suspension, and dissolved at 90 °C with stirring. ND content versus PVA was controlled as 0~10 wt%. PVA/ND aqueous suspension was cast at room temperature, then dried in vacuum at 40 °C for 48 h. The film thickness was controlled as 100 μm.

Measurements

X-ray diffraction was performed on an X-ray diffractometer (Rigaku, RINT2100) with Ni-filtered CuK α radiation. The X-ray beam was generated at 40 kV and 20 mA. The 2θ scan data were collected at 0.02 degree intervals at a scanning speed of 1.0 degree/min. X-ray diffraction photographs were recorded on imaging plate.

Infrared spectrum of ND was collected using FTIR spectrometer (Perkin Elmer Co., Ltd., spectrum GX FT-IR System I-KS) using KBr method. The spectrum data was collected from 4000 cm⁻¹ to 400 cm⁻¹.

ND particles and the cross section of PVA/ND nanocomposite were observed using a scanning electron microscope (JEOL, TSM-5610LVS), at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. Pt/Pd was deposited on the surface of the samples prior to the observation.

The constant thermal conductivity was measured by precise and prompt thermal-property measuring instrument (Kato Tech Co., Ltd., KES-F7). The thermal conductivity k (W/m·K) can be obtained from the following equation.

$$k = \frac{W \cdot D}{A \Delta T} \quad (\text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}) \quad (1)$$

W : Thermal loss of heat plate (W)

D : Thickness of sample (m)

A : Area of heat plate (m²)

ΔT : Temperature difference of sample (K)

The melting point (T_m) was measured by a differential scanning calorimeter (Seiko Instruments Inc., DSC-220CU). A heating rate was 10 °C/min under nitrogen flow. The thermal decomposition temperature (T_d) was measured by a thermogravimeter (Seiko Instruments Inc., TG/DTA-220CU). T_d was determined as a temperature of 5 wt% thermal weight loss.

Stress-strain curve was measured by a tensile tester, Autograph AGS-1kND (Shimadzu Co.) at room temperature. Initial length was 20 mm and the extension rate

was 2 mm/min. Dynamic storage modulus measurements were performed with a dynamic mechanical analyzer, DVA-220S (ITK Co., Ltd.), under nitrogen flow. A heating rate was 6 °C /min, and a frequency of 10 Hz was employed.

The UV/vis transmittance spectra were obtained using a UV/vis spectrometer (Hitachi Ltd., U-2000) at a wave length scan rate of 400 nm/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structure

Figure 1 shows the X-ray diffraction profiles of as-cast PVA/ND nanocomposites as well as that of ND particles. On the profile of the ND particles, the diffraction peaks assigned as 111 and 220 reflections were observed clearly at 43.9 ° and 75.3 ° in 2θ , respectively. These indicate the ND particles possess three dimensional diamond structure. This 111 reflection appeared in PVA/ND nanocomposites with ND content over 5 wt%, being overlapping with the 202 reflection of PVA.

Figure 1 X-ray diffraction profiles of PVA/ND nanocomposites.
a) $2\theta = 10 \sim 85^\circ$ b) $2\theta = 35 \sim 50^\circ$.

Figure 2 shows the FT-IR spectrum of the ND particles. Strong absorption bands assigned as hydroxyl groups appeared in the spectra area of $3500\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1620\text{--}1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [5]. These are due to water adsorption, because hydroxyl groups are easily absorbed on ND in air due to the many dangling bonds on the diamond structured surface [6]. The spectral area of $1620\text{--}1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is connected with several band superposition. The peak at 1628 cm^{-1} can be also attributed to stretching vibration of

aromatic C=C bonds. Absorption bands in the spectral area of 2920-2960 cm^{-1} and 2830-2880 cm^{-1} are assigned to the alkyl group [7]. Some carbonyl and carboxyl groups can be also observed from the absorption bands in the 1730-1790 cm^{-1} and 1100-1370 cm^{-1} regions [5, 7].

Figure 2 FT-IR spectrum of ND particles.

Figure 3 shows the SEM of a) ND, and b) PVA/ND nanocomposite with 5 wt% ND loading, respectively. From Figure 3 a), the individual size of ND particles were found to be up to 10 nm. Figure 3 b) indicates that these ND particles almost well dispersed in the PVA matrix. However, small agglomerates of ND particles with the size of 100-200 nm can be observed in the cross section of the nanocomposite as shown in the corner.

Figure 3 SEM photographs of a) ND particles, and b) the cross section of PVA/ND nanocomposite with 5 wt% diamond loading, respectively.

Thermal Properties

Thermal conductivity of the PVA/ND nanocomposites is shown in Figure 4. It reveals as much as 35 % increase in thermal conductivity with 10 wt% ND loading. The relationship between the thermal conductivity and the particle content has been explained with the effective medium theory for polymer-nanoparticle composites [8]. This theory predicts a decrease in the conductivity for small spherical particles due to the particle-matrix interfacial thermal resistance. In contrast, an increase can be seen for filler with high aspect ratio with sufficiently small interfacial resistance [9]. The increase in thermal conductivity observed in this research will suggest that ND particles have formed some agglomerates within the PVA matrix, which serve as thermally conducting channels. With sufficiently low particle-particle and particle-matrix thermal resistance, conditions can be met that will increase the overall thermal conductivity of the nanocomposite [10].

Figure 4 Relationship between the thermal conductivity k and the ND content of the PVA/ND nanocomposites.

Figure 5 shows the DSC thermograms of PVA film and the PVA/ND nanocomposites. Table 1 summarizes glass transition temperatures (T_g), melting temperatures (T_m), thermal degradation temperatures (T_d) and enthalpies (ΔH) of fusion for PVA film and the PVA/ND nanocomposites. The endotherm assigned as the melting of pure PVA (around 225 °C) was clearly observed in every case. Though the T_m of PVA/ND nanocomposites were similar to that of pure PVA, the corresponding ΔH decreased as the ND content increased. The ΔH of the PVA/ND nanocomposite with 10 wt% diamond loading decreased 33 % compared with that of PVA. This corresponds to the change in the crystallinity from 42 % to 28 %, assuming $\Delta H_0 = 159$ J/g [11]. From the DSC curves, small increase in T_g by the incorporation of ND particles was observed. This result can be confirmed by the data of the dynamic mechanical analysis shown below.

Figure 6 shows the temperature dependence of the mechanical $\tan\delta$ of the PVA/ND nanocomposites. The T_g dispersion shifted to higher temperature from 62 °C for PVA to 69 °C for the PVA/ND nanocomposite with 1 wt% diamond loading. This suggests that the introduction of ND particles into PVA leads to the pronounced suppression of PVA dynamics [12].

Figure 5 DSC thermograms of PVA film and PVA/ND nanocomposites.

Table 1 Thermal properties of PVA film and PVA/ND nanocomposites.

	T_g °C	T_m °C	ΔH J/g	T_d °C
PVA	62	225	66	263
PVA/ND 1 wt%	69	226	66	267
PVA/ND 5 wt%	69	226	51	277
PVA/ND 10 wt%	70	223	44	269

Figure 6 Temperature dependence of mechanical $\tan \delta$ of PVA film and PVA/ND nanocomposites.

Mechanical Properties

Diamond is known with its highest Young's modulus more than 1000 GPa. When the diamond particles are introduced in the PVA matrix as filler, Young's modulus is

expected to increase remarkably compared with that of PVA. As a first approximation, this increase can be predicted using simple rule of mixture with the following equation.

$$E_c = E_f V_f + E_m (1 - V_f)$$

where E_c , E_f , E_m are Young's modulus of the composite, diamond and PVA, respectively. V_f is the volume fraction of diamond. Assuming, E_f , $E_m = 1076$ GPa, 3.7 GPa, and 1 wt% ND loading corresponds to $V_f = 0.005$, E_c is estimated as 9.06 GPa.

Figure 7 shows the stress-strain curves of PVA and the PVA/ND nanocomposites from the tensile tests. The relationship between the Young's modulus (Y) and ND content of the PVA/ND nanocomposites was shown in Figure 8.

Table 2 summarize Young's modulus (Y), tensile strength (σ_{\max}) and elongation at break (ϵ_{\max}) of the PVA/ND nanocomposites. The Y and tensile σ_{\max} values increased drastically by the incorporation of ND. The Y value of nanocomposites displays about 2.5 times higher than that of PVA film, and it reaches 9.7 GPa for the PVA/ND nanocomposite with 1wt% ND loading. This value coincides with the calculated one shown above. The σ_{\max} increased from 95 MPa for the PVA film to 124 MPa for the PVA/ND nanocomposite with 5wt% ND loading. These suggest that the filler size of ND is small enough, and outstanding mechanical properties of diamond are imparted to the nanocomposite effectively.

Figure 7 Stress-strain curves of PVA film and PVA/ND nanocomposites.

Figure 8 Relationship between Young's modulus (Y) and ND content of the PVA/ND nanocomposites.

Table 2 Young's modulus (Y), tensile strength (σ_{\max}) and elongation at break (ϵ_{\max}) of PVA film and PVA/ND nanocomposites.

	Y GPa	σ_{\max} MPa	ϵ_{\max} %
PVA	3.7 ± 0.2	95.3 ± 2.5	72.7 ± 3.1
PVA/ND 1 wt%	9.7 ± 0.6	115.8 ± 5.2	41.2 ± 5.6
PVA/ND 5 wt%	10.6 ± 0.8	124.3 ± 5.4	16.1 ± 2.9
PVA/ND 10 wt%	9.2 ± 0.4	126.8 ± 3.0	4.5 ± 1.4

Figure 9 shows the temperature dependence of the storage modulus (E') of the PVA/ND nanocomposites. The E' value was enhanced when ND particles were incorporated. Especially, above T_g , the decrease of E' was suppressed for the PVA/ND nanocomposites compared with that of PVA. This is because when materials turn to be soft, the reinforcement effect of the ND particles determines the characteristics of the composite due to the restricted movement of the polymer chains [13].

Figure 9 Temperature dependence of storage modulus (E') of PVA/ND nanocomposites.

Transparency

Figure 10 shows the optical transparency of PVA film and the PVA/ND nanocomposites. PVA film exhibits more than 90 % transparency across the visible light spectrum. Though the PVA/ND nanocomposite with 10 wt% ND loading shows low transparency with almost below 50 %, the PVA/ND nanocomposite with 0.1 wt% ND loading shows high transparency close to that of PVA film.

Figure 10 UV-Vis spectra of PVA film and PVA/ND nanocomposites. The thickness was 100 μm .

CONCLUSIONS

From structural studies, by adding PVA to the ND aqueous suspension, ND particles were well dispersed in PVA matrix. The thermal decomposition temperature and the thermal conductivity increased when the ND particles were introduced. In addition, the T_g of PVA also increased. It reveals that incorporation of ND particles into PVA leads to the pronounced suppression of PVA dynamics. Further, Young's modulus and the tensile strength dramatically increased compared with those of PVA, especially the Young's modulus was 3 times higher compared with that of PVA with only 1 wt% ND loading.

Accordingly, it was revealed that PVA composite with nanodiamond possess remarkable properties, which can be prepared by simple method.

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